

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING PIANO PERFORMANCE IN CHILDREN'S MUSIC AND ART SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the pedagogical, artistic-aesthetic and developmental significance of teaching piano performance in children's music and art schools from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The issues of forming musical hearing, sense of rhythm, technical skills, creative thinking and artistic taste in students through piano lessons are highlighted..

Introduction.

Today, children's music and art schools play an important role in the formation of students' aesthetic taste, development of creative potential and provision of professionally oriented musical training. In particular, the piano, as a universal tool for musical education, plays a leading role in developing students' musical hearing, sense of rhythm, technical and performing skills.

Piano performance is distinguished from other instruments by its wide opening up of opportunities for polyphony, harmonic thinking, and understanding of musical form. Through this instrument, students develop the skills of reading music notation, analyzing musical text, mastering performance techniques, and consciously using artistic means of expression. This process has a positive effect not only on the acquisition of musical knowledge, but also on the intellectual, emotional, and psychological development of the child.

In the process of modernization of the education system in our country, special attention is paid to improving the content and quality of art education. From this point of view, one of the urgent issues is the effective organization of piano education in children's music and art schools, improving teaching methods based on modern pedagogical technologies. An individual approach in piano lessons, taking into account age and psychophysiological characteristics, and the correct organization of independent exercises are important factors in revealing the performing potential of students.

Piano performance in the practice of children's music and art schools is manifested as a complex pedagogical system that serves not only to teach an instrument, but also to educate and develop a person. It introduces the student to musical literacy, regulates his thinking, educates his emotions, and gradually forms his creative independence. Therefore, when talking about the pedagogical possibilities of piano performance, it is necessary, first of all, to

recognize that it is a “universal educational tool”: it turns listening to, understanding, analyzing, and artistic expression of music into a single process.

The greatest pedagogical power of the piano is in the systematization of musical thinking. The keyboard of the instrument is a visual “musical space” in which the order of sounds, intervals, chords, tonalities, and modulations become clear and tangible to the student. As a result, the child learns not only to play melodies, but also to understand the internal structure of music. For example, even a simple cadence or gamma exercise carries a great pedagogical load: it simultaneously requires control through hearing (intonation), control through hand movements (motor skills), and control through consciousness (thinking). This triad — hearing, movement, thinking — is the “integrative” feature that distinguishes piano education from many other areas.

Piano lessons comprehensively develop musical hearing. Here we are not talking only about “ear for melody”, but also about the harmonious formation of skills such as harmonic hearing, polyphonic hearing, timbre differentiation (separation of sound direction), rhythmic hearing. In the process of playing different textures and sound directions with two hands, the student is forced to “hear” several musical layers at the same time. This strengthens cognitive skills such as dividing attention, separating the main and secondary elements, and following musical logic. In addition, the piano is one of the most convenient areas for entering polyphony: starting from simple two-part works, the student learns to “speak” with equal leading, phrasing, breathing and dynamics of the voices. Another important layer of pedagogical opportunities is the formation of will and work culture through technical education. In piano, “technique” is often measured only by speed or finger dexterity, but in fact, technique is the conscious organization of movement, muscle economy, coordination, and synchrony with inner hearing. In the process of practicing, the child learns to make a plan, divide the goal into small steps, identify a mistake and choose a strategy to correct it. These skills also transfer to general educational activities: a student who regularly practices piano often becomes more disciplined and attentive in other subjects. Most importantly, qualities such as endurance, patience, and regularity in work where the result is not immediately visible are strengthened. Piano performance also has strong potential for educating the student’s emotional world. Music is the language of emotions, and the piano is a wide-ranging instrument that can “speak” this language. Through expressive means such as dynamics, agogy, articulation, and pedaling, the student practically feels that a piece can be interpreted in different ways. This raises the question of aesthetic evaluation, artistic decision-making, the creative question of “what do I want to say?” The child gradually begins to understand performance as a process of creating meaning, not just playing notes correctly. At this point, the teacher performs an important pedagogical task: he does not “load” ready-made emotions onto the student, but directs him to find an image within the musical text, to consciously choose means of expression.

The pedagogical value of piano education is also reflected in its communicative and socializing capabilities. Solo, ensemble, and concertmaster practice teach the student stage culture, communication with the audience, responsibility and self-control. In particular, ensemble performance instills in the child a sense of cooperation, listening and adapting, respect for others, and responsibility for the overall result. Concertmastering teaches the

student to understand the role of leader and accompanist, to build a musical dialogue, and to be a support for the soloist. These skills will later be useful not only in musical activities, but also in social life.

The pedagogical possibilities of the piano instrument are largely determined by the choice of repertoire. Repertoire is not just a list of works, but an educational roadmap. At the initial stage, works that strengthen technical foundations and simply express musical images are important, while at later stages, works that reveal stylistic differences (classicism, romanticism, modern musical language), with different textures and different characters, expand the student's musical worldview. In this process, the teacher should lead the child not only to a "difficult piece", but also to a "meaningful performance": sometimes an artistically perfect performance of a simple piece is more educational than a superficial playing of a complex piece.

Modern educational approaches open up new pedagogical horizons for piano lessons. For example, methods such as reflection (the student's analysis of his own performance), purposeful practice, metacognitive strategies (understanding how he learns), self-observation through audio/video recordings, small projects and performances (mini-recitals) strengthen the student's independence. Digital resources (metronome, audio monitoring, notation viewing programs) can also be used judiciously in piano education, but they should not replace live listening and artistic thinking, but rather strengthen them. That is, technology is a tool, and the goal is musical thinking and artistic expression.

It is worth noting that piano lessons require an individual approach. Each student has different psychophysiological characteristics, hand structure, attention stability, emotional type, and motivation. Piano pedagogy allows you to work taking into account these differences: some have strong hearing, others have rhythm; some memorize quickly, others slowly but deeply; some have strong stage fright, others vice versa. If the teacher can correctly read this "individual map", piano education will strongly form a culture of self-confidence, self-awareness, and self-improvement in the child.

The theoretical and practical knowledge accumulated so far in teaching students to play a musical instrument, in particular, the piano, and in the process of forming their musical performance abilities, skills and qualifications in children's music and art schools is characterized, on the one hand, by effective scientific research aimed at certain problems of musical and aesthetic education of amateurs of musical instruments, and on the other hand, by the development of a scientifically based integrated system of providing students with excellent musical and aesthetic education, and the lack of identification of the most important forms (categories) of such a system, such as the theory, practice, methods and means of teaching students to play the piano.

The lack of a comprehensive methodological system and educational and methodological resources that would enable students who wish to learn the piano to successfully master the performance of this instrument, as well as its organizational and methodological foundations, is due to the fact that educational institutions are not sufficiently provided with them, and the methodological training of many teachers and musicians working there is relatively inadequate, the aesthetic attitude of students to the art of music is not sufficiently formed, and musical and performing activities have not acquired a social

character. The fact that performance skills are formed in a scattered manner in instrumental lessons, that individual performance does not systematically incorporate practical musical skills in ensemble performance, and that there are no connections between various types of activities aimed at music perception, performance, and musical creativity, seriously hinder the provision of excellent musical education to students. The need to take into account the age and capabilities of students when organizing educational activities in the piano class has been emphasized in many literatures.

Also, the most important components are skills and competencies, namely the formation of academic, thematic, and intellectual skills. As a result of studying, analyzing scientific, methodological, and educational literature on the most important tasks set for piano lessons, and as a result of our personal observations, we came to the conclusion that it would be appropriate to work based on the following factors:

- Instrumental lessons (teaching system) should be based on musicology and the system of teaching piano playing (School of Piano Playing);
- Striving to cultivate the skills of perceiving and feeling music in the learning process;
- Organizing lessons as a discipline, taking into account additional knowledge when determining its specific structure and the procedure for mastering them;
- Taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of the student and directing them to creative activity;

In this case, it is necessary to integrate certain educational and educational activities into the general content of the activity, such as performing skills, independent and creative work with music, analysis of musical works, their artistic and aesthetic evaluation, performance and oral interpretation of musical works.

In order for piano classes to not be limited to a narrow area such as mastering certain works, exercises, performance techniques, and skills, in this process, it is necessary to involve children in interrelated types of activities aimed at attracting and motivating them to music. These include studying, playing, practicing and mastering technical skills in the process of mastering works of various genres, forms and styles, reading from a sheet, accompanying, playing in a group with a leader, playing by ear, copying sounds (badiha, improvisation).

The teacher requires that the various types of activities within the framework of teaching the piano be generalized around the main task of the student, without separating them from each other. In this case, creative inquisitiveness, initiative, resourcefulness, and methodological preparation are also required from the teacher himself.

The performance repertoire selected for reading and listening to music from a sheet (chitka) serves the development of the student's musical imagination, thinking, and perceptual abilities.

In conclusion, piano performance is a multifaceted educational process with wide pedagogical potential in children's music and art schools. It simultaneously develops musical literacy, hearing and thinking, technical skills, aesthetic taste, will and discipline, stage culture and social skills. Most importantly, piano education forms the student's ability to "understand and express music": this ability is the foundation of any musical activity, leading the child to a conscious relationship with art.

References:

- 1.Алексеев А. Д. Методика обучения игре на фортепиано. – М.: Музыка, 2017. – 288 с.
- 2.Гольденвейзер А. Б. О фортепианном исполнительстве. – М.: Музыка, 1975. – 276 с.
- 3.Uszler M., Gordon S., Smith S. The Well-Tempered Keyboard Teacher. – New York: Schirmer Books, 2000. – 356 p.
- 4.Bastien J. Piano Pedagogy: A Handbook for Teachers. – San Diego: Kjos Music Press, 2015. – 198 p.

